

NANOSPRING FILMS FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL INTERFACES

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Keywords: Interfaces, Interfacial improvement, Thermo-mechanical coupling

ABSTRACT

Cu nanoscale spring films fabricated by Glancing Angle Deposition (GLAD) were studied for their mechanical compliance and reversible compressibility as a function of their spacing that varied in the range of 2000 - 3200 nm. The mechanical behavior under compression was measured from 200 μm^2 areas of nanospring films with the aid of a nanoindenter. The compressive modulus was as low as 200 MPa and increased with applied stress due to the intertwined nature of nanosprings, which came in contact upon compression. At small applied stresses (<5 MPa), the Cu nanospring films were ~500 times more compliant than bulk Cu, while they experienced no permanent deformation for compressive stresses as high as 25 MPa.

1 INTRODUCTION

The method of Glancing Angle Deposition (GLAD) [2] can produce a variety of ordered nano- and microscale structures, such as nanosprings and nanorods [1], which can form films with high compliance and resistance to plastic deformation. Past research has reported promising results with regards to the Young's and shear moduli of individual nanosprings and their films. Hirakata et al. used an atomic force microscope (AFM) to apply vertical and lateral forces on capped Ta_2O_5 helical nanospring films [3]. They found that the film's shear and Young's moduli were 2-3 orders of magnitude smaller than those of solid Ta_2O_5 . However, their experiments were performed using a sharp diamond tip, resulting in non-uniform stresses in the nanospring layer under load. Using an AFM, Liu et al. performed multiple compression tests on individual Si nanosprings within a bulk forest, having two different spring spacings [4]; the springs in the film with the larger seed spacing had larger wire and coil diameters. The average stiffness was nearly 4 times greater for the Si nanosprings with larger seed spacing, and the wire diameter was ~1.6 times that of the other nanospring type. However, these experiments did not actually provide the stiffness of individual nanosprings because the adjacent nanosprings in the film played a significant role, especially for large displacements. Seto, et al. examined the effective Young's modulus of 2 μm thick SiO microspring films with 1, 2, and 3 coil turns by using a spherical indenter with a tip radius of 100 μm [5]. They found that microspring films were approximately 10^3 times more compliant than dense SiO films. The spring film stiffness increased with the number of turns from 10.0 (Nm^{-1})/ μm^2 to 17.8 (Nm^{-1})/ μm^2 . A shortcoming of this study stems from the use of a spherical tip which results in non-uniform force distribution on the spring film. This issue was eliminated in the compression experiments conducted in this study by using a flat probe. Furthermore, each of the prior studies applied small normal spring deflections, approximately 15 nm [3], 100 nm [4] and 300 nm [5], which produced small strains. The experiments in this paper were designed to examine the effect of large strains on nanospring compliance and assess the limits of elastic performance of GLAD nanosprings.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cu nanosprings were fabricated by Micralyne, Edmonton, Canada, using GLAD on a seeded silicon wafer. The nanospring films were deposited with four different seed spacings, namely 2000 nm, 2400 nm, 2800 nm, and 3200 nm, which also controlled the details of the final nanospring geometries. Uncapped Cu nanospring films with 10 turns and 1000 nm pitch are shown in Figure 1 (a-d). Compression tests were performed on defined test areas rather than continuous films to ensure a

Figure 1: Cu nanosprings with seed spacings: (a) 2000 nm, (b) 2400 nm, (c) 2800 nm, and (d) 3200 nm.

Figure 2: Test area definition in a Cu nanospring film with 2000 nm seed spacing. (a) Initial milling produced a cylinder with fused edges. (b) Fine milling was used to remove the fused nanosprings at the edges. (c) The nanosprings outside of the cylinder were finally removed using a sharp blade.

uniform applied stress. The test areas were prepared using a focused ion beam (FIB) that provided the needed precision and the capability to define small areas that could be tested with a nanoindenter. For test area definition, first, a ring with an outer diameter of 35 μm and inner diameter of 20 μm was milled at 30 kV and 2.5 nA throughout the thickness of the nanospring film (Figure 2a). As a result of the initial milling, a fused layer of Cu and Si formed, surrounding the outermost Cu nanosprings. This layer was subsequently removed by further FIB milling at the lower power level of 30 kV and 0.79 nA (Figure 2b). Finally, the springs outside of each cylindrical test area were removed with a mechanical probe. This process created cylindrical test areas with negligible edge effects due to fused springs (Figure 2c).

Compression tests were performed using a nanoindenter with a 500 μm diameter circular flat punch. Each test area was subjected to a 10-cycle loading and unloading routine between 0 MPa and one of the following values of stress: 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 35, or 45 MPa. This wide range of stresses was chosen in order to examine the nanospring film stiffness at much higher strains (up to $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ axial displacement at the higher stress value) than previously measured (less than 300 nm axial displacement) [3-5].

3 RESULTS

The effective compressive modulus, E , was calculated from the slope of the load vs. displacement plot as

$$E = k \frac{H}{A} \quad (1)$$

where k is the slope of the loading or unloading curves, H is the height of the spring film where the slope, k , is computed, and A is the area of the compressed springs. The loading and unloading stiffnesses were calculated for each of the 10 cycles. A plot of the load vs. displacement data for a 2000 nm seed spacing test area subjected to 0-5 MPa is shown in Figure 3. The slope was extracted using the data in the range of 90-100% of the peak load of every cycle. In addition, the height, H , was calculated by subtracting the total displacement of the nanoindenter tip at 90% of the peak load from the initial height of the nanospring test area. The effective compressive modulus derived from loading and unloading data for all stress ranges is shown in Figure 4. The data are separated according to seed spacing.

Figure 3: Load vs. displacement plot of a Cu nanospring film with for 2000 nm seed spacing loaded in the 0-5 MPa range. Each curve is shifted along the x-axis for visual clarity.

The effective nanospring modulus increased with applied stress due to adjacent nanosprings coming in contact with each other, thus restricting further displacement. Figure 5 compares the average unloading moduli for all seed spacings. On average, the unloading modulus increased with seed spacing. This is because in GLAD process larger seed spacings result in springs with larger wire and coil diameter. The measured stiffness, varying between 200 MPa and 2.5 GPa for the range of applied stresses, is much less than that of bulk Cu (110-128 GPa).

The nanospring test areas were examined via an SEM before and after mechanical compression to record their heights and determine the amount of permanent deformation. Figure 6 shows the spring heights before and after removal of the applied stress for all four seed spacings.

Figure 4: Compressive stiffness of nanospring films with seed spacings: (a) 2000 nm, (b) 2400 nm, (c) 2800 nm, and (d) 3200 nm.

Figure 5: Compressive stiffness of Cu nanospring films with different seed spacings derived from unloading curves.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 6: Height measurements of Cu nanospring test areas with seed spacings (a) 2000 nm, (b) 2400 nm, (c) 2800 nm, and (d) 3200 nm.

The only substantial pre- and post-test height differences were established for 35 and 45 MPa applied stress, as shown in Figure 7. The permanent strain was 4-5% for all four nanospring types at the applied stress of 35 MPa. At 45 MPa, the permanent strain increased to 5% for 2000 nm, 6% for 2400 nm, 7% for 2800 nm, and 7.8% for 3200 nm seed spacing. This is potentially due to the fact that larger seed spacing resulted in non-ideal coil geometries that were more prone to buckling and shearing.

Figure 7: Permanent compressive strain of Cu nanosprings as a function of seed spacing.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study showed that the compressive modulus of Cu nanospring films can be more than 500 times smaller (at 5 MPa applied stress) than the stiffness of bulk Cu, which has important implications in interface engineering. The compressive nanospring film stiffness increased with applied stress due to interactions between adjacent springs which caused progressive stiffening. The highest compressive modulus for Cu nanosprings (~2.5 GPa) loaded at 45 MPa was at most 2.3% of the Young's modulus of bulk Cu. Furthermore, permanent strain was recorded only for applied stresses that were greater than 25 MPa: at 35 MPa stress, the permanent strain of Cu nanospring films was 4-5%, while at 45 MPa, the permanent strain increased from ~5% for 2000 nm seed spacing to ~8% for 3200 nm seed spacing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support by the Air Force Office for Scientific Research through Grant FA9550-13-1-0149 with Dr. B.L. Lee as the program monitor.

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